

The Influence of School Vision-Mission and Social Media Through the Teaching of Faith on Green Ethics Practices at Private High Schools in Jakarta

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Abstract:- Work scientific (thesis). aim For research and analyze influence vision and mission school and social media through teachings faith to practice ethics green at school Private Senior High School in Jakarta. The sample used in research This were twenty (20) informants lock on five (5) Schools Private Senior High School in Jakarta with use method study qualitative and snow-ball sampling technique . data later analyzed with using the Nvivo 12 Plus software. Research results This show that vision and mission school and social media influential significant to practice ethics green through variable mediation, that is faith. this result strengthened with: First, environmental morals life as reason basic and urge for application practice ethics green at school. Second, fifth school the Already apply practice ethics green. Third, there is continuous HR learning that implements utilization vision and mission school and social media. Continuous HR learning refers to the process of development and improvement knowledge, skills, and attitudes of school human resources (teachers, staff, management and parents) in matter values environment , practice sustainable, and responsible answer to nature. Learning This aim For equip human resources with more understanding_ deep about issues environment and inspiration they For implement practices green in activity everyday at school. Based on results study this, then writer recommend to management School Private Senior High School in Jakarta by way of general For apply sustainable HR management for the sake of creating supportive and encouraging environment _ practice ethics green , as well ensure that effort sustainable the become integral part of culture and governance everyday at school .

Keywords:- Vision-Mission, Social Media , Green Ethics, Faith, Human Resources Sustainable.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) made prediction about condition earth Now after analyze more of 14,000 studies climate. predictable that pollution by carbon dioxide _ bad cause temperature rises 1.5 degrees Celsius in One decade to come come. Report this also shows that burn material burn fossils and releases greenhouse gases glass to atmosphere earth will cause temperature earth

increase with the average magnitude is 1.1 degrees Celsius. Condition This heighten potency happening wave hot, rain resulting heavy _ floods and cyclones tropical. Additionally, source. Power always nature dredged from earth and cultivated with various method cause circumstances earth become No stable, thinning supply source Power nature and diversity live, worsen condition environment Because waste production. Problems environment life No solely problem technology or economics, but also problems Act behavior and culture. Temporary That technology and activities economy Possible just become reason destructive behavior _ environment life in a manner direct. Is an argument writer where $\neg$ individual beliefs , norms culture and institutions social guide development Act destructive behavior _ environment live. Next, must consider How individual and social behavior form perception they to environment live and how Possible individual, organizational, and instrumental values can perpetuate destructive behavior _ environment life that (Ditjen PP Kemenhumham, 2023).

One form concrete application ethics green in institution education is school green. School green is reduced school _ impact environment , improve health and performance students , form friendly character and behavior _ environment as well as increase literacy sustainability. School green strengthen optimal learning and at the same time aligned with principle efficiency source power and minimal pollution. There are a number research already done about presence and performance school green. In practice, a green school is the physical result of a planning, design and construction process that takes into account the performance of a building over its entire 50 to 60 year life cycle. The main focus of the entire process is to reinforce optimal learning, an objective that closely matches the parallel goals of resource efficiency and minimum pollution. Such buildings provide clean fresh air, a comfortable temperature range, abundant light, and low distraction from unwanted noise, while also maximizing resource efficiency, minimizing pollution, and teaching students the importance of innovation in the built environment.

There is widespread concern today that the existing development model appears to be clearly unsustainable. We are faced with an urgent need to change the way we live. We are urged to move away from behavior that relies on unsustainable consumption of resources, degradation of

ecosystems and exploitation of people, and move towards models that seek to enhance the well-being of all human beings within the confines of our planet. In addition, it cannot be denied that social media greatly influences continuing education. Schools that strive to implement green ethics will work hard with the unexpected influence of social media. In today's world, social media plays an indispensable role in the learning behavior of students or students to achieve continuing education. The impact of social media on the sustainability of education is an important and driving factor. The world has become a global village and the use of technology has made it a smaller world through social media and how that is changing instruction.

In the encyclical it is stated that environmental crises that need attention and need to be addressed immediately are (1) pollution and climate change, (2) water problems, especially the availability of clean water and diseases caused by declining water quality, (3) loss of biodiversity, (4) decreased quality of human life and moral decline, (5) global inequality, (6) weak international response to the environment. Based on the explanation above, awareness and concern for the integrity of the natural world is an important and urgent attitude to be possessed and developed in human beings who believe (Arif Kelabur, OFM, 2020).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. School Vision and Mission

Vision is a process of making description in a manner thorough and try imagine different future circumstances. Because basically related with thinking to front, vision must become part from the planning process normal strategy for any school and should become bone back positive and inspiring system. In relationship with school, vision defined as optimistic dream. However realistic about what are we want from school us, future circumstances are more liked and expected from school, as well giving purpose direction from A school (Sarah Bainbridge, 2020).

Vision and mission school is something most basic statement about values, hopes and goals For success future school ome. because That vision and mission school is key success A managed school in a manner professional and coloring behavior all inhabitant school. Remember vision and mission is guidelines the main underlying whole school program, then expected in implementation can drawn in all activities carried out by residents school, from there seen all development and improvement quality school. school mission is step operational or business For realize vision school the. Mission is adaptation concise from part vision that has formulated through more sentences operational. Statement mission more comprehensive and encompassing draft institution, nature service, reason existence institutions, parties served, as well principles and values to be become handle at the moment operate activity. Statement good mission is part important in create, implement, and evaluate strategies. Develop and communicate statement good mission is one stages most important in management education. (Dini Dwi Yustia Puteri and Prihantini, 2020).

B. Social Media

Digital media and networks social revolutionize method communication everyday, collaboration, information sharing, and consumption information (Hansen et al, 2018). Social media provides a way for people to find information quickly. The openness of social media is the reason why many people use it. Students and students are one of the largest groups of people using social media. Apart from studying, students in Indonesia have an important role in social situations, one of which concerns religious tolerance. Students can act as facilitators of religious harmony in Indonesia.

The development of Internet technology has made social media the most important communication channel in Malaysia. According to statistics released by Suruhanjaya Communication and Multimedia Malaysia, 93.3% of Internet users have used social media for various purposes in life and work (MCMC 2020). Social media has become a communication channel that can not only connect individuals inside and outside the organization, but is also an efficient business platform (Men, et al, 2020). Social media has brought an update in management organizations, starting from creating innovative business models so as to change the way of communication, collaboration, search and sharing of information (Ali-Hassan et al. 2018). Social media can also encourage organizational learning and innovation to increase productivity and organizational achievements and strategies when facing dynamic environmental changes (Cetinkaya & Rasyid 2018).

C. The Teachings of the Catholic Faith

From perspective faith, Catholic Church in a manner special) has talk and explain about his vitals issue sustainability natural environment. Catholic Church have concern and concern to phenomenon damage threatening environment wholeness creation. Through Encyclical Laudato Si published by Pope Francis, citizen the church in particular and everyone is invited do actions concrete For guard wholeness creation (Arif Kelabur, OFM, 2020).

Pope Francis introduced nearly four years ago the encyclical "Laudato Si', on the Care of Our Common Home," a summary of Catholic teaching and thinking about creation and humanity's role in it. With that, he clearly outlined the important task of caring for nature as Christians (Catholics), and positioned the global Catholic Church as a promoter in responding to climate change and environmental degradation that the world is currently facing. Pope Francis defines his encyclical as an appeal to "the entire human family." establishing "a new dialogue about how to shape the future of our planet." The intended dialogue is not just thinking about solutions but must be implemented in various concrete actions to better care for the home (earth) which is increasingly apprehensive. And on the issue of climate change, several policies must be made and developed immediately so that in the next few years, environmental pollution, exploitation of the use of natural resources, carbon dioxide emissions and other highly polluting gases can be addressed with a humane and friendly moral (ethical) awareness. environment. This is a challenge that also aims to develop sustainable human resources and initiatives which

are then implemented to preserve the earth as an actualization of the Catholic faith (Brian Roewe, 2019).

D. Green Ethics

Green ethics teach not quite enough human moral responsibility For protect environment. because that, is condition For utilise source Power in a manner efficient while guard impact environment in mind. goods company or service own Lots chance For obey impact environment Good with change method produce goods or services, change method process source material raw, or change design product so that minimize house gas emissions glass they or reduce impact dangerous from use product (Ambassador, at al 2019).

Green ethics in a manner positive influence HR performance and then contribute to development source Power man sustainable green in arrangement organization. this produces two consequences positive, ie learning innovation green and performance innovation green sustainable HR. When employees own the necessary knowledge For performance green, their (ethical) behavior related with performance green increase. Organization and its employees influenced and motivated by those aspects positive from ethics environment (Ha Junsheng, et al 2020).

E. Sustainable Human Resources (HR).

Human Resources sustainable can depicted as planned HR strategy patten or appear as well as intended practice _ For possible achievement objective financia , social and ecological at a time reproduce the HR base in period long. Sustainable HR own most significant interest for organizations (Chams and García-Blandón, 2019; Sukalova and Ceniga, 2020) that lead to innovation and success. Sustainable HR considered as one element most important from every organizations (Chams and García-Blandón, 2019) that have role important in various activity organization . It has enough impact big to continuity sector education. In particular, in institutions education tall , he own role important in sustainable university development (Galleli, Hourneaux Jr and Munck, 2019).

Swanson explained connection between HR practices and innovation For create skill organization For objective business, for one is innovation performance. Companies can classify and implement group strategic HR practices For stimulate tendencies and motivations employee For involve they in apply practice this (Ogbeibu et al ., 2020). HR practice has significant role in activity innovation. Enhancement innovation sustainable own ability For increase activity innovation organization that leads to more performance high. Purpose understand efficiency and innovation is For minimize expenses (cutting costs) or For maximizing efficiency source power” through innovation. because That is, sustainable HR own role important in activity innovation (Manzoor et al ., 2019; Singh et al ., 2020).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Paradigm is perspective or corner view research used containing researcher _ How researcher see reality, how learn phenomena, the methods used in research and the methods used in interpret findings. In context design research, selection paradigm study describe choice something trust that will underlying and giving guidelines the entire research process. Paradigm research used _ is paradigm Purposeful post positivism identify influencing factors Practice ethics green through teachings faith at school medium on private sector in Jakarta.

➤ Research Design/Strategy

The research design used is Case Studies case based on phenomenon happened in schools that have selected. explore something phenomenon Specific as problem research, then set group particular individual, place, time, or process in a manner specific to be focus search.

➤ Concept Definition

Definition conceptual is meaning from concept used, so make it easy researcher operate draft it in the field. Based on understanding such, then definition conceptual used in study This are vision and mission, social media, teachings of faith, and green ethics.

➤ Social Situation

In research qualitative No use term population and sample as used _ in study quantitative , but by Spradley called "social situation" or situation social consisting _ on three element namely : the place (place), actors (actors), and activities (activity) that interact in a manner synergistic . Study conducted in 5 schools Catholic Upper Middle School in Jakarta. Researcher is a school teacher Intermediate First in Jakarta. With thereby similar situation _ make it easy researcher For do research .

➤ Key Informants

Key informants are individuals who have specific knowledge, status, and certain communication skills, who are willing to share what they know with researchers. The researcher must develop a special relationship with several people so that information can be captured efficiently. In this study, the key informants were the school principal, vice principal of the curriculum division, educators and education staff and one student.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. General Description of the Research Object

Peace High School is School Intermediate First Catholic in a very strategic location namely on Jl. Duri Selatan V No. 29, West Jakarta. Founded in 1964 and managed by the Bunda Hati Kudus Foundation (YBHK). Be equipped with various facilities and means learning the latest , the very maximum in support development and progress Study student . Also supported with atmosphere learning that is comfortable , fun , friendly , and interactive as well as accompanied by very competent teachers in the field . The average teacher already experienced over 10 years _ in matter management

education and learning student . Not surprising when Peace high school graduates always achievement and character as well as always accepted at State Universities and Private favorite.

On my way activity learning experience rapid progress with carve various achievements in the field knowledge, arts and skills good at level district, municipality, province, national nor Southeast Asian level. this _ become good motivation _ For Keep going proceed give service to public wide in field education. In 1984, the management of the Bunda Hati Kudus Foundation chaired by Pastor PC Budi Raharjo, MSC and Chair of the Foundation's Board of Trustees (Father Tarsisius Leisubun , MSC) was built building Peace school which has four standing floor magnificent at Jalan Duri Selatan V No. 29 – Tambora District West Jakarta. New building This was inaugurated on October 3, 1985 by Mrs. Dra. LE Coldenhoff as Head of Regional Office Depdikbud DKI Jakarta and the Archbishop of Jakarta Mgr. Leo Sukoto , SJ.

Study carried out and occurred in 5 private high schools Catholics in Jakarta. Every school there are 4 informants key interviewees, ie Head School, Deputy Principal School Curriculum Section , Subject Teachers and Students. Interview process data collection to appropriate data processing with guidelines on research proposals . Five schools the namely Peace High School West Jakarta, Francis 1 High School Central Jakarta, Francis 2 High School - East Jakarta, Tarakanita 1 High School - South Jakarta and Fons Vitae 2 High School - North Jakarta.

For make it easy description findings and analyzing data, researchers display it based on formula problem and goal research. With use Nvivo (word cloud and chart node coding) for analyze the data then make it a number of coding which is theme For answer objective research.

➤ *Know Reason Ethics Green Important and Urgent for Practiced in School (Theme: Rules, Love, Care, Care, Environmental Morals Life, Greening, Behavior Human, Principle, Friendly Environment and Responsibilities Answer).*

Graph 1 Visualization theme Rule

Graph 2 Visualization theme Love

Graph 3 Visualization theme Guard

Graph 4 Visualization theme Nurse

Graph 5 Visualization Environmental Moral theme

Graph 8 Visualization Eco -friendly theme

Graph 6 Visualization theme Behavior Man

Graph 9 Visualization theme Responsibility _

Graph 7 Visualization theme Principle

➤ Explain Forms Application Practice Ethics Green at School Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta (theme : Effective Proportional and Greening)

Graph 10 Visualization theme Effective Proportional

Graph 11 Visualization theme Greening

➤ Explain Forms Application Practice Ethics Green at School Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta (theme : Effective Proportional and Greening)

Graph 14 Visualization theme Learning

Graph 12 Visualization theme Awareness

Graph 15 Visualization Sustainability theme

Graph 13 Visualization theme Awareness

V. DATA REDUCTION

As already _ exposed previously, five Schools Private Upper Middle School who become place each study represents five regions in Jakarta (North, East, Central, South and West). In obtaining data, researchers prepare interview written, oral, FGD, study library and browse files as well as documentation from schools the. Researcher complete interview written with interview verbal order more make it easy in data processing through Vivo. With thus, the data is increasingly valid and measurable. The data is processed and analyzed is data already reduced.

- Learning : linkage between vision-mission, faith and use of social media as means information and communication (12)
- Rules : at school there is rule For practice ethics green (1)
- Sustainability: fulfill need moment This without sacrifice ability future generations For fulfil need they alone. In context practice ethics green in school , sustainability plays a role important in create environment sustainable and responsible learning _ answer to environment nature (11)

So, based on results interviewing, coding in form theme , influencing factors practice ethics green at school Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta is Learning. this factor is themes answered by 12 informants or 60%.

VI. CONCLUSION DRAWING

Results of research data processing in schools medium on private sector in Jakarta is *first* , give environmental moral foundation life in determine urgency For demonstrate ethics green at school . *second* , forms application practice ethics green Already done by all school *third* , must built awareness that continuous learning and HR is the most influencing factors practice ethics green at school . Basic need strengthened and clarified . Continuity need prepared by real human resources dedicated For education in one sides and sustainability environment on the other .

VII. DISCUSSION

➤ Know the Reasons why Green Ethics is Important and Urgent for Practiced in Schools

Green ethics important and urgent For practiced in schools informants answered through graphs which are visualization themes.

• Rules theme Visualization.

Fundamental reasons ethics green important and urgent is rules at school. Only one the informant answered namely, the Deputy Head School part Curriculum (WKSJ) from SMA F2 with answer 6.14%.

• Love theme Visualization

Fundamental reasons ethics green important and urgent For For practiced in schools is love natural as implementation from appreciation faith. There were 3 informants who answered namely Teacher Tarkan 1 (GT1) 6.60%, Head F1 Schools (KSF1) 6.24% and F1 Teachers (GF1) 2.33%.

• Keeping theme Visualization

Fundamental reasons ethics green important and urgent For practiced in schools is environment natural must guarded as fellow creation / mutualism. There were 3 informants who answered, ie F2 Students (SF2) 12.44%, Peace Students (SD) 12.15% and FV Students (SFV) 5.19%.

• Visualization of the theme of Caring

Fundamental reasons ethics green important and urgent For practiced in schools is influence and quality from HR.

There were 2 informants who answered, namely Peaceful Teachers (GD) 5.52% and Peaceful Students 3.47%.

• Visualization of the theme of Environmental Morals

Fundamental reasons ethics green important and urgent For practiced in schools is associated moral attitudes and actions with preservation and protection environment natural as well as continuity ecosystem for generation moment this and the future . In answer formula problem (1) and purpose research (1), answers this is the most selected by the informant ie there were 5 informant, namely WKSJ1 5.13%, WKSJF1 5.03%, WKSJFV 4.83%, WKSJFV 4.83% and GFV 4.16%.

- The fundamental reasons for green ethics are important and urgent to be practiced in schools are attitudes and actions aimed at preserving and protecting the natural environment and creating sustainability. In answering the formulation of the problem (1) and research objectives (1), this answer is the most numerous other than environmental morals, chosen by informants namely there are 5 informants, namely GT1 5.57%, GF2 3.95%, KSD 2.55% , KFV 2.27% and KSF1 2.08%.
- The fundamental reason green ethics is important and urgent to be practiced in schools is the guidelines and values that guide action to achieve environmental preservation and protection goals. There was 1 informant who chose this answer, namely KST1 4.51%.
- The basic reason why green ethics is important and urgent to be practiced in schools is to create a learning environment that is sustainable and environmentally sound. There were 2 informants who chose this answer, namely SF1 8.12% and KSF2 4.43%.
- The fundamental reason green ethics is important and urgent to be practiced in schools is the role and actions that must be carried out by students, teachers, staff and other related parties to implement and support environmentally friendly sustainable practices in the school environment. There was 1 informant who chose this answer, namely WKSJF2 7.75%.

Application ethics green at school involve collaboration between students and sustainable HR For create environment supportive learning moral values, sustainability and responsibility answer to environment. With so, school can become receptacle meaningful learning and change for generation moment this and the future.

➤ Explain Forms Application Green Ethics Practice in Schools Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta

Forms application practice ethics green at school informants answered _ through graphs which are visualization themes.

• Graph 10. Visualization theme Effectiveness Proportional

Forms application practice ethics green at school Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta is effective and appropriate with condition school like Establish education and awareness programs about importance ethics green, collaboration between lessons, infrastructure friendly environment, dau program reset and management waste, policy use material very use, plant urban schools and

agriculture, campaigning and activism environment, usage technology friendly environment, plant plants, thrifty electricity and water, saving use paper, processing waste, education and training, use material friendly environment, etc. All informants in the sample school answer that school they has carry out the above activities in a manner concrete, namely GT1 6.43%, GD 6.38%, WKSKE2 6.10%, SF1 4.87%, GF1 4.67%, ST1 and SFV 4.56%, SF2 4.55%, GFV 4, 34%, GF2 4.12%, WKSKEV 3.72%, WKSKE 3.62%, SD 3.53%, KSFV and KSF1 3.10%, KSD 3.04%, KSF2 2.52%, KST1 2, 52%, WKSKE1 1.92, WKSKE1 1.05%.

• *Graph 11. Visualization theme Greening*

Forms application practice ethics green at school Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta is make step important For teach students and colleagues about values environment and sustainability like planting, tending plant guard cleanliness and behavior. There was 1 informant who chose answer this, namely ST1 5.32%.

So, form application practice ethics green at school Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta is effective and appropriate with condition school. All informants in the sample school answer that school they has carry out the above activities in a manner concrete. Graph 10 shows that at 5 schools the Already operate forms application practice ethics green in a manner varies, that is building education and awareness programs about importance ethics green, collaboration between lessons, infrastructure friendly environment, dau program reset and management waste, policy use material very use, plant schools and urban farming, campaigning and activism environment, usage technology friendly environment, plant plants, thrifty electricity and water, saving use paper, processing waste, education and training, use material friendly environment. a number initiatives and programs that can used For build awareness and practice ethics green at school. All initiative it is very relevant and impactful positive to environment and formation attitude student. Following is relationship with sustainable HR :

- Sustainable HR need developing integrated educational programs _ values ethics green in curriculum.
- HR is necessary Work together For integrate aspect ethics green in various eye lesson. This requires coordination and cooperation between teachers.
- HR is involved in planning and implementation friendly infrastructure environment, like use material building sustainable or technology energy renewable.
- Sustainable HR need coordinating recycling programs reset and management waste at school. They can educate student about importance sort waste and supports implementation of this program.
- Sustainable HR role in formulate policy school related use material very use. They must ensure that policy This implemented with consistent. HR also coordinates plant urban schools and agriculture, campaigning and activism environment, usage technology friendly environment, plant plants, thrifty electricity and water, saving use paper, management waste management, education and training kindly overall, sustainable HR play role key in

encourage and support various initiative form application ethics green at school. They No only play role as facilitator but also as example real in apply values environment in action daily them.

➤ *Identify Influencing Factors Green Ethics Practice in Schools Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta*

Identify influencing factors _ practice ethics green at school Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta were answered by informants in visualization themes.

• *Graph 12. Visualization theme Awareness*

Influencing factors _ _ practice ethics green at school Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta is deep understanding _ about importance environment, impact from action man to ecosystem, and urgency For take action positive in conserve nature. Selecting informants _ answer This there are 5, namely WKSKEV 8.65%, SF1 8.00%, WKSKE 5.12%, KSF1 4.38% and KSFV 3.55%.

• *Graph 13. Visualization theme Limitations*

Influencing factors _ _ practice ethics green at school Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta is place, knowledge, awareness, equipment, human resources and information. Selecting informants _ answer This there are 5, namely WKSKE2 6.18%, KST1 4.03%, WKSKEV 2.95%, WKSKE1 2.68% and KSFV 0.89%.

• *Graph 14. Visualization theme Learning*

Influencing factors _ _ practice ethics green at school Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta is linkages between vision-mission, faith and use of social media as means information and communication. Selecting informants _ answer This there is 12 or 60% of whole informants, namely KSF2 16.51%, KST1 16.22%, KSD 10.90%, WKSKE1 10.35%, WKSKE1 8.91%, SFV 7.47%, ST1 7.09%, GFV 7.00%, GF2 6.46%, KSFV 5.90%, GT1 4.65% and KSF1 2.21%.

• *Graph 15. Visualization Sustainability theme*

Influencing factors _ _ practice ethics green at school Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta is fulfil need moment This without sacrifice ability future generations _ For fulfil need they alone. In context practice ethics green in school, sustainability plays a role important in create environment sustainable and responsible learning _ answer to environment nature. Selecting informants _ answer This there are 11, namely GD 11.10%, KSD 11.06%, KSFV 8.51%, KSF1 8.50%, WKSKE2 6.73%, GFV 6.63%, GF1 6.47%, GF2 6.29%, KSF2 4.13%, WKSKE 3.04% and WKSKE1 2.68%.

So, the influencing factors practice ethics green at school Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta is learning: linkage between vision-mission, rules, faith and use of social media as means information and communication contained in graph 14. Informants who choose _ answer This there is 12 or 60% of whole informant. Learning as the most influencing factor tight relation with sustainable HR. Sustainable HR play role important in push and apply ethics green at school.

- Human Resources _ sustainable are the professionals at the school who have commitment to principles sustainability and environment .
- Human Resources _ sustainable role in integrate ethics green in curriculum , teach values environment , and deliver example action real in practice everyday .

With Thus, vision and mission , rules , faith , use of social media , and sustainable human resources Work together For create environment supportive and encouraging school _ application ethics green . When all element This each other support , ethics green will become part not inseparable from culture school and form behavior students and community school going to practice sustainable and responsible answer to environment .

➤ *Influence of School Vision and Mission to Practice Green Ethics in Schools Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta*

Vision and mission school own significant influence _ to practice ethics green at school Private Upper Middle School . Vision and mission school reflect goals and core values promoted by the institution education the . If practice ethics green in accordance with vision and mission school , then will become integral part of culture and environment study at school . Following is a number of the way in which vision-mission school can influence practice ethics green :

- Focus on Sustainability and Environment : If sustainability and environment become part from vision and mission school , then will There is strong commitment _ For apply practice ethics green . this _ can reflected in emphasized curriculum _ education environment , greening program , and efforts For reduce impact negative to environment .
- Alignment of Values with Green Ethics: Vision and mission citing school _ values like not quite enough answer social , caring to nature , or continuity will support practice ethics green . Students , teachers, and staff will more tend adopt values This in action everyday and be part from practice ethics green .
- Push Participation and Awareness : If the vision and mission school put importance participation active student in realize objective school , then practice ethics green will responded with more positive . Student will more pushed For involved in environmental programs and improve awareness about issues environment .
- Integrating Green Ethics in Policy School : Vision and mission stressed school _ importance ethics green can reflect in policy supportive school _ subtraction footsteps carbon , management wise trash , or _ use efficient energy and water .
- Important For noted that implementation practice ethics green at school No only depending on the vision and mission school , but also on commitment from whole community school , incl students , teachers, staff , and management school . Awareness and participation active from all party is key success in create environment sustainable and responsible learning _ answer to environment nature .

➤ *Social Media Influence to practice Green Ethics in Schools Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta*

- *Influence Positive :*
 - ✓ Awareness Environment : Social media can be a platform for spread information about issues environment and practice ethics green to student . Various campaigns , videos, and content environment can awaken awareness and inspiration student For take action sustainable .
 - ✓ Education and Experience Sharing : Students can share experience they about practice ethics green in schools , including greening programs , activities conservation , or effort subtraction waste . this _ can motivating and inviting other students for follow as well as in effort environment .
 - ✓ Engagement and Participation : Social media can become means For invite students and community school involved in environmental programs or campaign organized by the school or organization environment.
- *Influence Negative :*
 - ✓ Greenwashing: Several entity Possible using social media For spread misleading information _ about practice ethics green they without There is proof real . this _ can confusing students and reduce effectiveness awareness environment .
 - ✓ Ignorance or Indifference : Social media does too become place for students who don't care or not enough interested in issues environment . No information _ appropriate or not enough accurate can cause ignorance about importance ethics green and preservation environment .

For ensure social media influence impact positive to practice ethics green at school High School , important for schools and social media users , especially students , for use those platforms in a manner wise . Push source credible information , participate _ in meaningful campaigns , and discuss in a manner positive about issues environment will help increase awareness and contribution in practice ethics green at school .

➤ *Connection the Teachings of the Catholic Faith and Sustainable Human Resources to Practice Green Ethics in Schools Private Upper Middle School in Jakarta*

Connection between teachings faith Catholics and sources Power sustainable human resources _ _ important implications _ to practice ethics green at school Upper Intermediate . Following is a number of aspect connection these :

- Role as Manager God's Creation : Teachings faith Catholic teach that man is part from God's beautiful and trusted creation as manager nature . Source Power sustainable humanity _ in context This means confess value and dignity every individual and make man as factor important in preservation and preservation nature .

- Education and Training Sustainable : Source Power sustainable humanity _ involve continuing education and training _ For develop knowledge , skills , and attitudes that contribute to sustainability environment . At school , p This can covers education about ethics green , practice sustainability , and awareness will issues environment .
- Responsibility to _ Future Generations : Teachings _ faith Catholic push man For honor the future and leave good legacy _ for generation future . In context practice ethics green at school , source Power sustainable humanity _ means teach student For value importance action sustainable support _ continuity natural for the future .
- Solidarity and Justice Social : Teachings faith Catholic emphasize importance solidarity and justice social . Source Power sustainable humanity _ in context This means ensure that policies and practices ethics green at school also pay attention interests and welfare all party involved , incl students , teachers, staff , and the community around .
- Integration of Green Ethical Values in Practice Everyday : Source Power sustainable humanity _ covers integration values ethics green in practice everyday . This can reflected in decisions management , policy school , use source power , and participation active student in activity environment .
- School Parks and Urban Agriculture : Developing park schools and urban agriculture as part from education environment . Student can Study about agriculture organic , diversity life and benefits ecosystem .
- Campaigns and Activism Environment : Encouraging student For take role active in campaign environment and activism . With give they opportunity For participate in action real , they are will feel own significant contribution _ to change positive .
- Use Environmentally Friendly Technology : Applying efficient technology _ energy and friendly environment in operation school . For example , using light economical energy , system efficient cooler , or _ technology intelligent For control use energy .
- Certification Environment : Chasing certification or confession environment , like be an Eco-School or accept award related sustainability . It's not only is confession on effort green , but also can inspire another school for follow trail .
- Participation Active : Pushing participation active from all member community school , incl students , teachers, staff , and parents . Stage meeting routine or group Work about ethics green can help maintain passion and commitment .
- Implementation ethics green at school is journey sustainable . With combine some of the suggestions above , school can create sustainable culture , committed to sustainability _ environment , and deliver example positive to students and community .

With integrate teachings faith Catholic with source Power sustainable humanity _ in practice ethics green at school Middle School , school can create environment based learning _ supporting spiritual and social values continuity nature . This also helps _ form character student as responsible individual _ answer and be sensitive to need social and ecological in life they everyday .

VIII. MANAGERIAL ADVICE

- Education and Awareness : Building education and awareness programs about importance ethics green to students , teachers, staff , parents , and the community school . It will help all party understand impact environment from action them and motivate participation in practice green .
- Collaboration Between Lessons: Integration of principles ethics green in curriculum lesson can help student understand connection between environment , society , and economy . This too can stimulate creativity and thought critical student in look for solution For challenge environment .
- Green Infrastructure : Adopt _ friendly infrastructure _ environment throughout _ school , like system savings energy , source energy renewables , efficient water management , and design sustainable building .
- Recycling and Management Program Waste : Apply system cycle effective replay and promote _ management waste wise throughout _ _ school . This can involve gift necessary training and facilities _ for students and staff .
- Policy Use of Single Use Materials : Reduce or remove use product plastic very use and replace it with more alternatives _ friendly environment . Invite student bring stock food and drink in receptacle myself can too help reduce rubbish plastic .

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